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**Current response to atmospheric low pressures
travelling north and south of Ormen Lange**

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Abstract

The second largest gas field in Norway, Ormen Lange, is located at Storegga about 140 km west of Kristiansund in mid Norway. The area is situated in the continental slope in the upper part of the Storegga slide, with varying water depth from 700 to 1100 m. A prominent feature of the area is the extremely rough bottom topography which locally affects the currents significantly.

Measurements from moored instruments in the area have revealed short term events with a sudden change in temperature accompanied by strong currents. Some of these events are clearly induced by atmospheric forces, others have so far not been given an explanation.

At shallow locations (less than 500 m) the Atlantic Water is dominant. Here drops in temperature are found, indicating an up-welling of colder water. At deeper locations both increase and decrease in temperature are measured. If the low pressure activity is forcing these events, then both up- and down-welling should be found in the numerical results when idealised atmospheric low pressures force the model.

A three-dimensional, time split, σ -coordinate model is used to simulate travelling idealised low pressures entering north and south of Ormen Lange. The results show that low pressures that enter north of Ormen Lange will first generate a down-welling due to Ekman transport in the surface towards land, enhanced transports in the along shelf direction and enhanced Ekman veering to the left in the bottom boundary layer. Low pressures entering south of Ormen Lange produce up-welling because of Ekman transport in the surface away from land.

1 Introduction

An ongoing data acquisition program at Ormen Lange, an offshore gas field located in the Storegga region off mid-Norway (Figure 1), has identified several events in which the currents close to the seabed exhibit peak values in their speed and temperature over a short period of time. This may cause problems for near seabed installations needed for developing the gas field. It is therefore important to understand the generation mechanisms of these events and their extremes, to investigate the possibility of forecasting them.

Earlier reports (e.g., Eliassen et al. 2000) have commented on these events and suggested two plausible explanations for the high current speeds occurring at Ormen Lange. Internal waves that break towards the shelf slope or currents at strong internal density fronts. Both these explanations indicate the connection between very strong local effects and larger scale internal wave phenomena. The most pronounced generation mechanism behind internal wave phenomena in this area is atmospheric forcing (Vikebø et al. (2001)) and the tide.

Several numerical simulations have been carried out to investigate in more detail the effect an idealised atmospheric travelling low pressure has on the currents and the isopycnals at the Norwegian shelf slope. This has been done by changing the radius and magnitude of the low pressure, or changing the path (Vikebø et al. (2001)). Numerical experiments have been done where the combined effect of an atmospheric low pressure and the thermohaline field on the currents were investigated (Thiem et al. (2001)).

So far the focus has been on storms passing north of Ormen Lange. In the present study, the response of the system to low pressure passing to the south of Ormen Lange will also be studied.

From stationary Ekman theory, the transport in the upper layer (Ekman layer) will be at an angle of 90° to the right of the wind direction. This means that wind from the south along the Norwegian coast will give a transport in the upper layer towards the coast. The flow along the shelf edge in the along slope direction will be enhanced. Ekman veering in the bottom boundary layer will be to the left. This veering will be strengthened and move water masses in the bottom boundary layer towards greater depths, creating a down-welling situation. When the wind comes from the north, there will be a transport out from the coast and the shelf edge. Up-welling of deep water along the shelf slope will take place to compensate for the transport off the shelf edge.

The initial conditions for velocities, salinity and temperature are from Eldevik et al. (2001). These initial conditions correspond to several months (165 days to be exact) spin up from the climatological data of Engedahl et

Figure 1: Model area given in grid coordinates. The grid size is 20 km. The Ormen Lange area is outlined. The colour bar indicate depths in meters.

al. (1998), producing relative strong thermohaline fronts.

Figure 2: Ormen Lange with the locations OL1-OL5.

The model result will be visualised by time series of the speed, velocity and temperature, 10m above the seabed. The time series will be taken from

5 different locations in the Ormen Lange area. See Figure 1 and Figure 2. The depth at the locations are given in Table 1.

Location	OL1	OL2	OL3	OL4	OL5
Depth	257.0	499.0	835.9	1120.1	764.4

Table 1: Depths in meters at stations OL1 to OL5

2 Model

This model study uses the numerical σ -coordinate ocean model of Berntsen (2000). The equations are the continuity equation for an incompressible fluid, the Reynold averaged hydrostatic momentum equations, conservation equations for temperature and salinity and the UNESCO-equation of state. The reader is referred to Berntsen (2000) for further details concerning the governing equations and numerical methods.

The model area covers the Norwegian Sea basin, see Figure 1. The horizontal grid size is 20 km. In the vertical, 30 σ -layers are applied and these are distributed according to a formula given in Lynch et al. (1995). Their formula distributes the layers symmetrically about the midpoint in the vertical with a gradually finer resolution towards the surface and the bottom.

The model is run for 240 hours with an internal 3-D time step of 360 s. There are 30 2-D time steps per 3-D step. Initial values of water elevation, velocities, temperature and salinity are taken from Eldevik et al. (2001). At the lateral open boundaries, except at the boundary to the Baltic, a flow relaxation scheme (FRS) is implemented (Martinsen and Engedahl, 1987). The FRS-zones are 7 grid-cells wide. In addition to the initial values for water elevation (η), velocity (u and v), temperature (T) and salinity (S), four tidal constituents (M_2, S_2, K_1, N_2) are used to specify the lateral boundary conditions.

The flow to and from the Baltic is implemented after an algorithm due to Stigebrandt (1980). Fresh water runoff from 27 rivers around the North Sea is included. For experiments over longer periods this forcing will strongly affect the coastal circulation, but in the present study this forcing has minor importance.

Travelling low pressure systems are important driving mechanisms for the oceanic flow. Martinsen et al. (1979) constructed a model of a cyclone and studied barotropic effects of the moving cyclone. The atmospheric pressure

disturbance is described by, following Martinsen et al. (1979),

$$p(x, y, t) = p_0(t)e^{\{-(x-x_0-u_0t)^2+(y-y_0-v_0t)^2\}/R^2} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where $p_0(t)$ is the pressure disturbance at the center of the cyclone, x_0, y_0 the initial position of the center of the pressure disturbance, u_0, v_0 are the x and y components of the propagation velocity and R defines the horizontal extent of the pressure disturbance. Wind velocity components u_g and v_g in x and y directions, respectively, are computed from the gradients in the atmospheric pressure.

$$u_g = -\frac{0.7}{f\rho_a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \quad , \quad (2)$$

$$v_g = \frac{0.7}{f\rho_a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \quad . \quad (3)$$

Above f is the Coriolis parameter and ρ_a the density of the air (1.3 kgm^{-3}).

From the wind velocity, wind stress is computed

$$\tau_x = \rho_a c_D (u_g^2 + v_g^2)^{1/2} u_g \quad , \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_y = \rho_a c_D (u_g^2 + v_g^2)^{1/2} v_g \quad , \quad (5)$$

where c_D is the drag coefficient. In our experiments c_D is chosen to be 3×10^{-3} (cf. Martinsen et al. 1979).

A finding of Vikebø et al. (2001) is that the strongest response of the currents at Ormen Lange occurs when the maximum wind speed was approximately along the shelf slope. In the numerical experiments in this report, the low pressure path is located such that it will give maximum wind speed approximately along the shelf slope.

The model is first run for 24 hours with $p_0(t) = 0$. The low pressures are then started at positions (x_0, y_0) , given in grid coordinates, see Table 2. The pressure disturbance $p_0(t)$ is increased linearly over the next 12 hours to -60 hpa, and held constant for the remaining simulation period. The propagation velocities are $u_0 = 8.59 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and $v_0 = -4.81 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ in both experiments

Experiment		x_0	y_0
NORTH	(RUN_R500)	-21.1	100.4
SOUTH		-34.0	65.0

Table 2: Experiments in this paper. In parentheses the corresponding simulations in Vikebø et al. (2001).

Figure 3: The two storm paths with time in hours.

which give the paths shown in Figure 3. In the experiments the radius of the idealised atmospheric low pressure $R = 500$ km. This will give a maximum wind speed 354 km ($R/\sqrt{2}$) from the center of the low pressure.

3 Model results

Time series of current speed at Ormen Lange are presented in Figure 7. It is evident from this figure that the maximum speed peak is higher for the two shallowest stations when the low pressure enters north of Ormen Lange. This is probably because the area with maximum wind speed for this low pressure is passing directly above the Ormen Lange area, see Figure 4. For the deepest location (OL4) it is the low pressure passing south of Ormen Lange that gives the maximum current speed.

The low pressure passing south of Ormen Lange gives an increase in the speed followed by a fall prior to the main speed peak. This early increase in speed is also found in the figures for velocity, figures 8 and 9. This speed fluctuation is connected to flow in the opposite direction prior to the main velocity peak. This is due to the passage of the southern low, giving a northern wind at first and a down-welling situation because of the Ekman transport in the surface towards land, see Figure 4 b). Then the wind direction changes towards a more southern direction, giving Ekman transport in the surface off coast and an up-welling situation.

At OL1 the rise in temperature due to the low pressure center passing to the north, is much less than the decrease due the low pressure center passing to the south. The magnitude of the current velocities are approximately the same at OL1. The fact that the temperature changes less when the low passes north, can be explained by the down-welling that arises. The internal water (Atlantic Water) at the shelf is more homogeneous in temperature, with a cold surface layer, see Figure 6 a). The cold surface layer is transported towards the coast by the Ekman transport, Figure 6 b). This results in transport of Atlantic Water along the shelf and shelf slope. The water passing OL1 during a down-welling will therefore have less gradients in the temperature than the water coming up under an up-welling, Figure 6 c).

Figure 6 also shows that the amplitude of the oscillations of the thermaline field during the passage of a strong low pressure, can be at least 200 m. This is an amplitude that can be difficult to measure since the water close to the Norwegian shelf is separated into distinct layers, see Helland-Hansen (1909). Each of these layers has almost constant temperature and salinity, while there are strong gradients on the interface between the layers, see Figure 5.

The thickness of the flow layer up and down along the shelf slope depends on the direction of the flow, see Figure 6. When the atmospheric low pressure passes to the north, there will be a down flow of water with less density than the surrounding water. This is an unstable situation, that generates a significant amount of mixing, which will give a thick flow layer along the shelf slope. When the low pressure passes to the south, the up flow layer will be relatively thin due to the stable situation that arises when heavy water rises below lighter water. This produces less mixing and a thinner flow layer as seen in Figure 6 c).

When the low pressure is passing to the north of Ormen Lange, the fluctuations are more harmonic and stable than for low pressures passing to the south. When the low pressure is passing north, it passes the deep water in the Norwegian Sea. This will give rise to inertial oscillations with periods around 13.3 hours in the deep open ocean. These oscillations will be less affected by the bottom friction since the friction layer is very small compared to the interior of the ocean. When the low pressure center is passing south of Ormen Lange, it passes an area with relatively shallow water depths. This means that the the forced flow will be stronger affected by the bottom friction and oscillations will damped more rapidly. The thickness of the flow layer can also affect the oscillations. When the atmospheric low pressure passes to the north of Ormen Lange, the flow layer is relatively thin and stable. With a thin and stable bottom layer the oscillations may experience less damping than with a thick and unstable layer, which we get when the atmospheric

(a) Low passing north of OL3.

(b) Low passing south of OL3.

Figure 4: Time series of wind and temperature at OL3. Arrows in the x-direction indicate wind velocities in the x-direction, or along shelf, in the model domain. Arrows in the y-direction indicate wind velocities in the y-direction, or cross shelf, in the model domain.

Figure 5: Mean profiles of temperature, salinity and density measured at the Ormen Lange area. Figure from Johan Blindheim, private communications.

low pressure is passing to the south of Ormen Lange.

4 Discussion

Atmospheric low pressure systems with centers in the open Norwegian Sea will create southern winds at Ormen Lange. Due to the Ekman transport in the upper layer to the right of the wind, or towards the coast, there will also be a compensating off-shore under current. The general flow in the along shelf direction will be strengthened. The Ekman veering in the bottom boundary layer is to the left and will move water masses in the near-seabed layer downwards.

In contrast, when the atmospheric low pressure systems have their centers to the south, that is in the Norwegian Sea, they will create northerly winds at Ormen Lange. The surface Ekman transport will move water masses off the shelf edge and create a compensating up-welling of colder water masses in the near sea bed layer at the shelf slope.

During down-welling along the seabed at the shelf slope, lighter water masses will be moved underneath heavier water masses. This will create almost immediate mixing and the bottom boundary layer will become thicker. During up-welling, heavier water masses will move up underneath lighter water masses. The stability will be increased and the up-welling will occur in a relatively thin layer.

The results from the present studies show that the model is able to produce results that are consistent with the general knowledge about the response of the ocean to the wind forcing. For both scenarios in this report, the water masses will be moved vertically from their equilibrium levels due to wind forcing. *Down* when the low pressure center is to the north and *up* when the low pressure center is to the south. As the wind forcing weakens, the water masses will try to flow back to their equilibrium levels and this is seen as oscillations in the time series. In particular when the low pressure center is in the deep Norwegian Sea, there will be strong inertial oscillations of large volumes of water masses that die out slowly due to frictional forces.

In this model experiment a model with 20 km grid resolution is applied. Earlier reports (Thiem et al. (2002)) have shown that numerical results are sensitive to the grid resolution. In particular the amplitudes of the oscillations seem to be reduced as the grid resolution is refined. This means that there are frictional forces on a sub-grid scale that are not represented well with 20 km grid resolution.

The stratification is important for the response of the ocean to the forcing. So far most experiments have been performed with smooth climatological val-

(a) Initial field for temperature.

(b) Low passing north of Ormen Lange.

(c) Low passing south of Ormen Lange.

Figure 6: Rising and sinking of the thermohaline field. Temperature in degrees after 84 hours b) and c). The x -axis are in km.

ues of temperature, salinity and density. In reality, there is a strong interface between the Atlantic Water and the Norwegian Sea Arctic Intermediate Water, see Figure 5. Both measurements and model studies show that extreme values in velocities and sudden changes in temperature are often connected to oscillations of this interface. The future work should, therefore, focus more on situations with hydrographic profiles similar to those presented in Figure 5.

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(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 7: Time series of speed OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Low passing north (bold line), and south (thin line) of Ormen Lange.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 8: Time series of velocity in x-direction OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Low passing north (bold line), and south (thin line) of Ormen Lange.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 9: Time series of velocity in y-direction OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Low passing north (bold line), and south (thin line) of Ormen Lange.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 10: Time series of temperature OL1-OL5, 10m above the sea bed. Low passing north (bold line), and south (thin line) of Ormen Lange.

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